

Trafficking Nanosugars through Lymph Node Tissues for the Delivery of Small and Large Bioactive Molecules

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ABSTRACT

Targeted delivery of therapeutics to lymph nodes (LNs) *via* minimally invasive subcutaneous injection offers promise to treat B and T cell malignancies, latent HIV-1 reservoirs, and cancer metastasis. However, achieving therapeutic drug levels in subcutaneous tissues and LNs is challenging because of the poor retention and accumulation of soluble drugs. Engineered nanoparticles (NPs) provide a platform for prolonging drug stability and retention in the subcutaneous space and LNs, acting as reservoirs for the sustained release of drugs through the lymphatic system. Yet, their clinical translation for LN drug delivery faces limitations owing to the potential immunogenicity and toxicity of NP material components. Herein, we show that glycogen, a natural and biodegradable polysaccharide NP—nanosugar—can be tailored by controlling its size, surface charge, and functional groups to enable the delivery of small and large bioactive molecules in LNs. Upon subcutaneous injection, positively charged nanosugars primarily accumulate in the liver and kidneys, whereas negatively charged nanosugars accumulate in the liver and lungs, irrespective of their size. Small and positively charged (19 ± 2 nm; 53 ± 4 mV) nanosugars accumulate more efficiently in LNs than the large and positively charged (57 ± 2 nm; 54 ± 9 mV) or small and negatively charged (13 ± 4 nm; -27 ± 1 mV) nanosugars. Moreover, smaller and slightly positively charged nanosugars (16 ± 4 nm; 10 ± 6 mV) enable the loading and delivery of Cre-recombinase mRNA, small organic molecules and antibodies at the site of injection

and LNs. The nanosugars are associated with macrophages lining the subcapsular sinus and medullary regions of the LNs but are also detected within the paracortex at the T cell zone. This suggests that the nanosugars can overcome the phagocytic cells barrier by saturating the phagocytic capacity of the macrophages at the subcapsular sinus and spread to deeper parts of the paracortex region, providing an avenue for their application in the treatment of lymphatic diseases.

Therapeutic delivery to lymph node (LN) tissues has gained interest owing to its potential to treat B and T cell malignancies, latent HIV-1 reservoirs, and cancer metastases, as well as enhancing vaccines and immune tolerance.¹ LN supply of pharmaceuticals can be attained by leveraging intravenous (IV), subcutaneous (SC), or intramuscular injection. Unlike IV and intramuscular administration routes, which typically require patient hospitalization, intervention of healthcare professionals, and cause physical pain and distress to the patient, SC administration of therapeutics offers an attractive minimally invasive approach.^{2,3} However, the SC administration of soluble drugs, *e.g.*, anticancer drugs and immunostimulant cytosine–phosphate–guanine oligonucleotides, typically results in poor retention of the drugs at the injection site and LN tissues, thereby reducing the efficacy of treatment.^{4,5}

Nanoparticles (NPs) offer a platform to encapsulate drugs of different molecular weights and pharmacological activities (*e.g.*, small chemotherapeutics, messenger RNA (mRNA), antibodies, and peptides), prolonging the stability of the drugs and serving as reservoirs for their sustained release through the lymphatic system.^{2,6} For instance, NP-mediated delivery of antigens, adjuvants, and radiopharmaceuticals to LNs is a standard practice for vaccination against COVID-19,⁷ as well as for diagnosing breast cancer metastasis.⁸ Various NPs have been engineered for drug and vaccine delivery by leveraging lymphatic transport mechanisms upon

SC injection including lipid-based NPs,^{9, 10} synthetic polymers,^{1, 11-13} block copolymer micelles,^{14, 15} natural biopolymers,¹⁶⁻²⁰ and inorganic NPs.²¹⁻²³ However, the clinical translation of SC-administered NPs is limited, with only liposomal formulations being marketed for postoperative pain management and advanced to phase II/III clinical trials for the treatment of multiple sclerosis, and prostate, rectal breast, and myeloma cancer.² Some of the factors hindering the development of NPs for LN drug delivery include complex synthetic routes, lack of reproducibility at large scale, high cost of production, and toxicity of synthetic materials.²

NP transport through the SC space depends on electrostatic and size exclusion interactions of the NPs with the extracellular matrix (ECM). NPs that are >100 nm in size are typically retained at the injection site owing to size exclusion, with subsequent LN transport mediated by antigen-presenting cells over hours to days.^{2, 24} NPs that are 10–100 nm in size exhibit high diffusivity, reaching LNs within minutes to hours, after SC injection, whereas 10 nm NPs may bypass LNs and enter systemic circulation.²⁵ In addition, the lymphatic system itself pose a size exclusion effect, which is mediated by the size of the openings in the initial lymphatic vessels that innervate the interstitium.

Surface charge also influences transport. Neutral or negatively charged small NPs are more efficiently transported to LNs, whereas positively charged NPs interact with the negatively charged ECM components thus displaying limited mobility.²⁶ For instance, it was reported that negatively charged 30 nm lipid NPs reached the LN paracortex more effectively than neutral or positively charged lipid NPs.²⁷ NP rigidity further impacts LN penetration, with flexible polymers (*e.g.*, dextran) showing higher accumulation at LNs than rigid spheres. A study reported that 2% of injected 30 nm flexible dextran polymer chains accumulated within LNs in contrast to only 0.2% observed for similarly sized but rigid polystyrene spheres, suggesting that

the flexibility of polymer chains aids diffusion inside LNs.²⁵ Lastly, surface functionalization with poly(ethylene glycol) (termed as PEGylation) is a commonly used strategy to reduce aggregation and enhance LN access but it can induce anti-PEG immune responses and lead to accelerated blood clearance and PEG accumulation in phagocytic cells.^{28,29}

Therefore, to expand the potential of LN-targeting NPs, it is essential to develop nontoxic and degradable PEG-free NPs to afford simple physicochemical modifications, drug loading/release properties, large scale production, and limited batch-to-batch variability. In this context, glycogen, a naturally occurring highly hydrated, soft, and deformable porous polysaccharide NP (15–50 nm) with a dendrimer-like structure³⁰ obtained by large-scale manufacturing processes, offers a universal platform for easy functionalization, loading of small hydrophilic/hydrophobic drugs and large molecules (peptides, proteins, and nucleic acids), while maintaining high water solubility.^{31,32}

We have shown that glycogen NPs—termed as nanosugars—functionalized with amine and boronated groups enable fast and sustained glucose-responsive insulin delivery in diabetic mice up to 13 h post SC injection, with optimal bioavailability, pharmacokinetics, and safety profiles.³³ In addition, we have shown that nanosugars can engage T cells without the use of receptor-targeting antibodies and enable intracellular drug release to reactivate HIV-1 latently infected Jurkat T cells and mRNA.³⁴ Hence, we propose the use of glycogen NPs for the delivery of bioactive molecules to immune resident cells in lymph nodes.

In the present study, we investigated the trafficking and accumulation of glycogen NPs in different organs and LN tissues, upon SC injection, *in vivo*. Our findings showed that positively charged glycogen NP primarily accumulated in the liver and kidneys, whereas negatively

charged glycogen NPs accumulated in the liver and lungs. Moreover, we found that small positively charged glycogen modified with ethylenediamine (EDA) (SG_{EDA} NPs) accumulated more efficiently in LNs following SC administration compared with the large positively charged EDA-containing glycogen (LG_{EDA} NPs) or small negatively charged carboxyl group-modified glycogen (SG_{COOH} NPs). SG_{EDA} NPs enabled the successful intranodal delivery of various cargos, including mRNA, small molecules, and antibodies. SG_{EDA} NPs were detected both within the subcapsular sinus (SCS) area of the LNs, rich in macrophages (CD169⁺), and in the paracortex zone where resident T cells (CD3⁺) are located, suggesting their ability to overcome barrier cells and accumulate in deeper areas of LN tissues. Overall, these results show the potential of glycogen NPs for a broader range of applications, which might include lymphoma treatment and antigen delivery.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

***In Vivo* Biodistribution, Circulation, and Toxicity of Engineered Nanosugars after SC Administration.** Nanosugars derived from plant and animal sources, intrinsically different in size, were engineered with different surface charges to evaluate the influence of their physicochemical properties on *in vivo* biodistribution, lymphatic transport, accumulation at LNs, association with different cell populations, and delivery of small and large cargo molecules upon SC injection. To engineer positively charged glycogen NPs, following a methodology previously developed by our group, EDA was incorporated into large glycogen NPs (LG NPs, derived from plants) and small glycogen NPs (SG NPs, derived from bovine liver) through a reductive amination reaction to obtain LG_{EDA} NPs (~50 nm) and SG_{EDA} NPs (~15 nm), respectively (**Figure 1A**).³⁴⁻³⁶

By varying the amount of EDA used, the degree of substitution (DS) and consequently the surface charge of the NPs (ζ -potential) were controlled, as confirmed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (**Figure S1**). The size and surface charge of LG_{EDA} NPs and SG_{EDA} NPs were characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and electrophoretic mobility measurements as displayed in **Table S1**. $\text{LG}_{\text{EDA-20}}$ NPs and $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs with DS of 20% (ζ -potential 54 ± 9 mV) and 27% (ζ -potential 53 ± 4 mV), respectively, were obtained (**Figure 1B**). $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-6}}$ NPs with DS of 6% and a lower surface charge (ζ -potential 10 ± 6 mV) were also prepared for comparative studies and to demonstrate the ability of $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-6}}$ NPs to deliver mRNA, small-molecule dye, and antibodies to the LNs.

Negatively charged glycogen NPs were prepared by esterification reactions with succinic anhydride. This resulted in the formation of LG_{COOH} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs exhibiting negative ζ -potential values of -36 ± 3 mV and -27 ± 1 mV, respectively (**Figure 1B**). The modification of glycogen NPs by carboxyl groups was confirmed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (**Figure S1**) and quantified (DS 14–17%) by potentiometric titration (**Figure S2**). Of note, the modification of the NPs with amine or carboxyl groups slightly influenced the NP size as shown by DLS (**Figure 1C**).

To evaluate the biodegradability of glycogen NPs in conditions that mimic biological fluids and intracellular environments, α -amylase and β -amylase digestion assays were conducted respectively. The analysis was performed at 37°C for 3 h using amylase levels typically found in plasma (α -amylase) and cellular lysosomal compartments (β -amylase). The data in **Table S1** indicated that LG NPs (nonmodified glycogen NPs), LG_{COOH} NPs, and $\text{LG}_{\text{EDA-20}}$ NPs were resistant to α -amylase digestion in the first 3 h incubation, undergoing approximately 7% degradation, whereas SG NPs (nonmodified glycogen NPs), SG_{COOH} NPs, and SG_{EDA} NPs ($\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs and $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-6}}$ NPs) degraded partially, up to 24%, 10%, and 15% respectively. The

charged glycogen NPs modified with amine or carboxyl groups were also resistant to β -amylase digestion, with $\leq 12\%$ degradability observed. In contrast, $\sim 40\%$ of degradation was determined for both unmodified LG NPs and SG NPs after treatment with β -amylase. Overall, these results suggest that upon SC injection, aminated and carboxylated nanosugars likely preserve their integrity and structure in the extracellular and intracellular milieu.

To obtain insights into the lymphatic uptake, systemic circulation, blood clearance, and organ distribution of the nanosugars, cyanine 5.5 (Cy5.5)-labeled NPs were subcutaneously administered at a concentration of 6 mg mL^{-1} ($200 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$) into the flank of C57/BL6 mice. At 1 and 24 h postinjection, the mice were humanely killed, and major organs (heart, liver, spleen, lung, kidney, and brain) and skin at the site of injection were isolated for *ex vivo* fluorescence imaging (**Figure 1D**). Representative images of animal organs (**Figure 1E**) indicated that at 24 h post SC injection, all the NPs were mainly localized at the injection site, independently of their physicochemical properties. Blood clearance of the nanosugars was also monitored over 24 h postinjection (**Figure S3**). An increase in the fluorescence signal corresponding to 0.2–0.4% of the injected dose was observed in the blood after 1 h, which remained steady up to 24 h of observation. This finding suggests that all glycogen NPs enter the blood stream by a sustained slow release from the subcutaneous depot. After entering the blood stream, $\text{LG}_{\text{EDA-20}}$ NPs accumulated primarily in the liver (**Figure 1E**), confirming our previous finding,³³ *i.e.*, positively charged LG NPs are sequestered and processed by liver hepatocytes and finally undergo either intracellular hepatic degradation or hepatobiliary excretion *via* the bile duct. Contrarily, $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs were cleared and retained in the kidney, likely due to their small size and positive charge. The $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs, which are approximately 19 nm in size, can potentially pass through the kidney glomerular endothelium fenestrations (70–80 nm).³⁷ However, the glomerular basement

membrane, composed of a 300-nm-thick connective tissue membrane rich in negatively charged heparan sulphate (pore size of 2–8 nm) can arrest the SG_{EDA-27} NPs by electrostatic and size exclusion effects.³⁷⁻³⁹ Negatively charged LG_{COOH} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs showed a higher deposition in the liver and lung tissues. It was recently shown that negatively charged mRNA-metal–phenolic network NPs could accumulate in lung tissues.⁴⁰ The lung-associated activity could be attributed to nonspecific interactions or protein corona-mediated specific association to lung capillaries.⁴¹ Studies are underway to investigate the effect of the protein corona on the biodistribution of the nanosugars. Limited accumulation in the spleen was observed for all glycogen NPs, suggesting low capture by the spleen reticuloendothelial system regardless of the size or surface charge of the nanosugars.

We also examined the presence of the nanosugars in various LNs after SC injection. All glycogen NPs transited through the LNs, with accumulation of SG_{EDA-27} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs observed at the inguinal and axillary LNs (**Figure 1F**). The biocompatibility of all the glycogen NPs was confirmed by histological characterization of the different organs. As indicated by hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, no detectable toxic effects were present after treatment for 1 or 24 h (**Figure 1G** and **Figure S4**).

Figure 1. *In vivo* biodistribution of glycogen NPs after SC administration. (A) Synthesis of neutral (SG NPs, LG NPs), positively charged (SG_{EDA-27} NPs, LG_{EDA-20} NPs), and negatively charged (SG_{COOH} NPs, LG_{COOH} NPs) NPs. Positively charged NPs were prepared by functionalizing bare (neutral) glycogen NPs with amine (EDA). Negatively charged NPs were obtained by introducing –COOH groups through esterification reaction with succinic anhydride.

DMAP, 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine. **(B, C)** NP characterization was performed using DLS to determine ζ -potential **(B)** and size by number **(C)**. **(D)** Schematic representation of the *in vivo* experimental setup used to study Cy5.5-labeled glycogen NP biodistribution. **(E)** Cy5.5 fluorescence images of skin and major organs, harvested at 1 and 24 h post SC administration of the NPs. **(F)** Cy5.5 fluorescence imaging of LNs, 24 h after SC injection. cLN: contralateral LN; iLN: ipsilateral LN. **(G)** Representative H&E histological samples of different tissues collected 24 h after SC injection. Scale bar for all images: 100 μm .

Influence of NP Surface Charge and Size on LN Trafficking of Nanosugars. To better understand the distribution and cellular localization of $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs within LNs, SC administration of the NPs was repeated but *via* a different route, *i.e.*, injection of the nanosugars labeled with Alexa Fluor 647 (AF647) at the mouse's hind hock. Detailed analysis of the popliteal LN tissue by confocal microscopy was performed after labeling macrophages, B cells, and T cells with CD169, CD45R, and CD3 antibodies, respectively. The results confirmed lymphatic drainage of $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs and their accumulation at the popliteal and inguinal LNs 5 h postinjection as shown in **Figure 2A** and **Figure S5**. $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs were mostly localized to the SCS and likely phagocytosed by macrophages. $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs were also found localized deep in the paracortex area of the LN, rich in T cells, at 1 h postinjection (**Figure 2B**). This finding suggests that transport of the nanosugars is independent of dendritic cells (DCs), as DC-dependent trafficking of NPs would result in a slower transport (approximately 10 h) compared to the direct convective transport of NPs.⁴² Collectively, the data indicate that the $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs rapidly move from the SC space to the periphery of the LN at the SCS and then to the parenchyma before the arrival of migratory DCs.

Similarly, negatively charged SG_{COOH} NPs, with size comparable to that of SG_{EDA-27} NPs (**Table S1, Figure 1C**), were injected into the ankle of mice and the distribution of the nanosugars within the popliteal LNs was analyzed 1 h post administration. Representative confocal images showed limited accumulation of SG_{COOH} NPs at the popliteal LN tissue, with their location being restricted to the SCS (**Figure 2C**).

To evaluate the integrity and cellular localization of SG_{EDA-27} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs in the LNs with nanoscale resolution, the tissue was analyzed by super-resolution single molecule localization microscopy (STORM) (**Figure 2D** and **Figure S6**). STORM images revealed that the SG_{EDA-27} NPs diffused into the LN as intact, nondegraded NPs, and appeared to be associated with the cell membrane. Intact nondegraded SG_{COOH} NPs were also detected by STORM, although to a lower extent (**Figure 2D**), which is in accordance with the nanosugar accumulation detected by confocal microscopy.

We next investigated the effect of NP size on the diffusion of the NPs through LN tissues. The large positively charged glycogen (LG_{EDA-20}) NPs were injected subcutaneously at the animal's hind hock, and the popliteal LNs, collected 1 and 5 h postinjection. As observed by confocal microscopy, LG_{EDA-20} NPs were found at the SCS, most likely phagocytosed by macrophages, after 1 h (**Figure S7**). However, LG_{EDA-20} NP retention at the LN tissue appeared to occur at a lower extent than that of the smaller SG_{EDA-27} NPs.

Overall, the findings suggest that SG_{COOH} NPs transit rapidly through the lymph, from one LN to the next LN, limiting association with macrophages and infiltration inside LN tissue. In contrast, SG_{EDA-27} NPs are retained at the LN tissue after SC injection and can overcome the SCS macrophage barrier to then move deeper into the paracortex T cell-rich zone (**Figure 2E**). Of

note, previous studies have reported that negatively charged lipid NPs of 30 nm in size translocate to the LNs and deep cortex more efficiently than neutral or positively charged lipid NPs and are primarily phagocytosed by DCs at the injection site.²⁷ Our study suggests a different trend where the softness³⁰ and positive charge of SG_{EDA-27} NPs are key determinants for the deep transport of cargos in the LNs.

Figure 2. Intranodal nanosugar trafficking and retention after SC administration. (A, B) Representative confocal images of the popliteal LN at 5 h (A) and 1 h (B) post administration of

positively charged NPs (SG_{EDA-27} NPs). AF647-labeled NPs are identified in cyan. Scale bars: 100 μm . (C) Representative confocal images of the popliteal LN 1 h after administration of negatively charged NPs (SG_{COOH} NPs). AF647-labeled NPs are identified in cyan. Scale bar: 100 μm . (D) Representative STORM images of AF647-labeled SG_{EDA-27} and SG_{COOH} NPs. Scale bars: 6 μm and 100 nm (magnified inset images). (E) Schematic representation of glycogen NP accumulation at the LN tissue after SC administration. SG_{EDA-27} is retained at the SCS and paracortex, whereas SG_{COOH} NPs transit faster through the lymph, limiting cellular uptake even from barrier cells such as macrophages.

Small Positively Charged Nanosugars Enable the Delivery of mRNA and Transfection of LNs Via SC Administration. Given the biodistribution profiles of the glycogen NPs upon SC injection, their biocompatibility, and the ability of positively charged SG_{EDA} NPs to accumulate in the LNs, we investigated the potential of these NPs for *in vivo* mRNA delivery to LN tissues.

As demonstrated in our previous study, SG_{EDA-6} NPs with a low surface charge (ζ -potential 10 ± 6 mV) can complex with mRNA through electrostatic interactions (to form SG_{EDA-6} -mRNA nanosugar complexes (NCs), **Figure 3A**) and achieve mRNA transfection *ex vivo* using primary human T cells;³⁴ therefore, these NPs were selected for the following studies. Firstly, we examined the biodistribution of the Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6} NPs injected in C57BL/6 mice (**Figure 3A**). Similarly to other types of nanosugars (**Figure 1**), many SG_{EDA-6} NPs remained confined at the injection site (skin) at 24 h post SC administration (**Figure 3B**).

However, the difference in the surface charge of the SG_{EDA-6} NPs yielded a different biodistribution profile. Compared with SG_{EDA-27} NPs with a ζ -potential of ~ 50 mV (**Figure 1E**), SG_{EDA-6} NPs with a ζ -potential of ~ 10 mV preferentially accumulated in the liver than the

kidneys (**Figure 3C**). Left and right axillary, inguinal, brachial, and cervical LNs were also collected and analyzed on an In Vivo Imaging System (IVIS). Among the LNs examined, left axillary and inguinal LNs displayed the highest accumulation of SG_{EDA-6} NPs (**Figure 3D**). This is likely explained by the physiology of the lymphatic system. After injection into the SC space at the left flank, the NPs will enter the lymphatic vessels and drain to the closest LNs, in this case axillary and inguinal LNs, before draining to downstream LNs and entering the blood flow.

Next, Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6} NPs loaded with mRNA (*i.e.*, SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs) were prepared and analyzed by STORM to study their size and shape. The size distribution of the SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs (**Figure S8**) was obtained using clustering analysis of molecule localization and showed an average size of 77 ± 40 nm (which agrees with the DLS measurements (**Table S1**)) and neutral charge, suggesting complexation with the negatively charged nucleic acids. The SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs were evaluated for transfection *in vivo*. An engineered mouse model (Ai14), genetically modified to express the red fluorescent protein tdTomato upon transfection with Cre-recombinase mRNA (Cre mRNA),⁴³ was used to assess the transfection efficiency of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs. The expression of tdTomato in these reporter mice is silenced by a loxP-flanked stop cassette, which is excised by the Cre enzyme to activate tdTomato expression.⁴³ Similarly to that described for SG_{EDA-6} NPs, SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs were injected in the left flank of Ai14 mice. After 24 h, organs were harvested and analyzed by IVIS, to determine tdTomato expression and biodistribution of the Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs. The SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs showed a biodistribution profile comparable to that of SG_{EDA-6} NPs, suggesting that the loading of the nucleic acid cargo (Cre mRNA) and the variation in size and surface charge did not significantly influence the overall accumulation of the NPs in the different organs during the first 24 h of treatment (**Figure 3E–G**). Analysis of the Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs by

IVIS and confocal microscopy confirmed the distribution pattern of the NPs at the site of injection (**Figure S9**) and within the LNs, *i.e.*, favorable accumulation of NPs in the left inguinal and axillary LNs. Of note, the expression of tdTomato was detected at the site of injection and within the axillary LNs (**Figure 3H, I**). Despite the accumulation of SG_{EDA-6} NP in the liver, no evidence of transfection was observed in this organ (data not shown). This finding suggests that either SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs are primarily sequestered in the LNs or upon entrance in the blood stream are likely exposed to enzymatic degradation. To verify this hypothesis, a similar formulation of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs was administered *via* IV injection and the biodistribution and transfection efficiency were studied after 24 h. As shown in **Figure S10A**, the accumulation of SG_{EDA-6} carrying mRNA (mFlame) at major organs is comparable to that of those administered by SC, *i.e.*, most of the NPs were found in the liver followed by kidneys. However, the average radiance of the NPs (administered by IV) measured by IVIS at the LNs, was lower than that of the NPs injected subcutaneously (**Figure S10B**, 6.6×10^7 *versus* 4.5×10^8 for axillary LNs; 6.1×10^7 *versus* 1.2×10^8 for inguinal LNs). This might be attributed to the additional burden of NP extravasation from blood vessels to the lymphatic system in addition to the rapid sequestration of the NPs by the liver and kidneys. While successful mRNA delivery and expression was observed in the liver (**Figure S10C**), indicating stability of the cargo, no transfection was detected in any of the LNs analyzed (**Figure S10D**). Additionally, to exclude the possibility of false-positive signals, we performed a control experiment in which naked mRNA was injected subcutaneously. The results in **Figure S11** show that naked mRNA is inactive under our experimental conditions. Overall, these results indicate that, after SC administration, SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs remain functional during circulation in the lymphatic and blood stream, however the majority of the mRNA is released and expressed in the LNs.

As mRNA loading in the SG_{EDA-6} NPs occurs mainly due to electrostatic interactions, we hypothesized whether a highly positive glycogen carrier would perform better for transfection. Therefore, we used SG_{EDA-27} NPs endowed with higher surface charge (ζ -potential 53 mV) for Cre mRNA loading and subsequent SC injection in Ai14 mice. After 24 h, the mice were sacrificed and major tissues analyzed by IVIS. As previously observed, most of the SG_{EDA-27}-mRNA NCs remained accumulated at the site of injection (**Figure S12A**), followed by the kidneys and liver (**Figure S12B**). In addition, a significantly lower NC accumulation, compared to SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA, at the LNs (average radiance efficiency: 2.4×10^7 versus 4.5×10^8 for axillary LNs; 9.1×10^7 versus 1.2×10^8 for inguinal LNs) was observed (**Figure S12C versus Figure 3G**), and transfection was only detected locally at the skin tissue (**Figure S12D**). Confocal microscopy showed that the NCs were taken up by cells at the injection site, with detectable transfection in the skin tissue, with fewer SG_{EDA-27}-mRNA NCs being sequestered by the macrophages at the SCS (CD169⁺, **Figure S12E**) of LNs. Nevertheless, transfection could not be detected at the LNs (data not shown). These results indicate that the significantly larger size (220 ± 100 nm) causes the SG_{EDA-27}-mRNA NCs to remain confined at the injection site with limited translocation to the LNs.

Figure 3. *In vivo* biodistribution and transfection potential of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NC administered subcutaneously. (A) Schematic representation of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NC formation and *in vivo* experimental setup. (B–D) Cy5.5 fluorescence images, acquired by IVIS, of skin (B), major organs (C), and LNs (D) harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6} NPs (ζ -potential 10 mV) in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. (E–G) Cy5.5 fluorescence images of skin (E), major organs (F), and LNs (G) harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs in the left flank of Ai14 mice. (H, I) tdTomato expression fluorescence images of skin (H) and LNs (I) loaded with Cre mRNA (SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA) in the left flank of Ai14 mice. Data are represented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Statistical analyses were performed by unpaired *t*-test (B, E, H), two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test (C, F), two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test (D, G), or one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test (I). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$, ns nonsignificant.

Literature reports describe the partitioning of NPs within LNs and cellular populations as a function of their size. Specifically, larger particles typically cannot access lymphocytes, which constitute the vast majority of resident cells at the LNs, but instead remain associated with barrier cells such as macrophages.¹ To obtain insights into the distribution of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs within the different cell populations present in the LNs, we used immunohistochemistry, and confocal and super resolution microscopies to distinguish the different cell types. The LNs were fixed and embedded in optimal cutting temperature (OCT) compound for sectioning and subsequent histology and immunohistochemistry studies. H&E staining of the LNs showed no signs of tissue pathology upon SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NC administration (Figure 4A). Initially, the LN tissues were stained for lymphatic vessel endothelial hyaluronic acid receptor 1 (LYVE-1) that is

expressed by the lymphatic endothelial cells. Confocal imaging revealed the SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs both at proximity of LYVE-1⁺ cells and dispersed within other regions of the LNs (**Figure 4B**). This finding indicates that the SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs drain from the SC space into the LN tissues *via* afferent lymphatic vessels, which are responsible for transporting unfiltered lymph into the SCS. Next, the morphology of the NCs found within the LN tissues was examined by STORM. For that purpose, the axillary LN tissue cryosections of mice previously treated with Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs were imaged. **Figure 4C** shows representative STORM images of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs within LN tissues and the size distribution quantified and plotted on a frequency histogram, revealing an average size of 87 ± 40 nm which is consistent with that measured for the nanosugar complexes in solution (77 ± 40 nm). This suggests that SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs maintain their structural morphology during translocation in the LNs.

The tissues were further stained with specific antibodies that recognize different cell populations within the LNs. In detail, CD3, CD45R, CD11c, and CD169 antibodies were used for the identification of T cells, B cells, DCs, and macrophages, respectively (**Figure 4D–G**).

Figure 4. SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs accumulate at LNs 24 h after SC administration. **(A)** Representative H&E histological section of an axillary LN exposed to treatment with SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs. Scale bar: 400 μ m. **(B)** Representative confocal images of the axillary LN stained for LYVE-1 to detect endothelial lymphatic cells (red). Cy5.5-labeled NPs are identified in yellow. Scale bar: 500 μ m. **(C)** Size distribution and representative STORM microscopy images of Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs detected within the axillary LN. Scale bars 1000 μ m and 100 μ m for inset. **(D)** Representative confocal images of the axillary LN stained for CD169, CD3, and CD45R to identify macrophages, T cells, and B cells, respectively. Cy5.5-labeled NCs are identified in yellow. Scale bar: 500 μ m (magnified area). **(E, F)** Representative super-resolution images acquired by SIM from the T cell region **(E)** and the LN medullary zone **(F)**. Scale bars for all images: 20 μ m. **(G)** Representative confocal images of the axillary LN stained for CD169, CD3, and CD11c to identify macrophages, T cells, and DCs, respectively. Cy5.5-labeled NPs are identified in yellow. Scale bars: 500 μ m and 100 μ m (magnified area).

From **Figure 4D** and **Figure S13**, SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs were found at the SCS and medullary sinus, where the macrophages are concentrated (CD169⁺, purple). SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs were also detected in deeper parts of the tissue, *i.e.*, the paracortex zone where T cells (CD3⁺, pink) are located, suggesting their ability to overcome the macrophage layer. However, NCs were not detected within B cell follicles (CD45R, cyan). To obtain a better insight into this phenomenon, the LN tissue was imaged by super-resolution structured illumination microscopy (SIM). The results showed some degree of NC accumulation within the T cell zone (**Figure 4E**), contrasting with the high accumulation of NPs at SCS (**Figure 4F**), which seem to be mostly associated with CD169⁺ macrophages.

The interaction of the SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs and SG_{EDA-6} NPs with DCs was also investigated. Similarly to macrophages, DCs are part of barrier cells that constitute the LNs. **Figure 4G** shows that little-to-none of the NCs accumulated within CD11c⁺ DCs, indicating that NC intranodal trafficking occurs independently of DC transport.

The typical delivery of molecules and NPs to the parenchyma of draining LNs is achieved *via* different pathways. These include transport *via* reticular conduits for ≤ 70 kDa molecules or through the SCS macrophages and DCs if NPs are loaded with antigen cargo.⁴² The latter process is therefore cell-dependent and occurs over the course of hours to days. Additionally, DCs can enter the T cell zone *via* pores in the SCS endothelium in interfollicular regions. Thus, NPs can potentially use the same openings in the SCS endothelium.⁴⁴ Furthermore, if the particles can overcome phagocytosis by SCS macrophages and DCs, they can keep travelling *via* the sinuses into the T cell zone.⁴⁴ Finally, antigens can be transcytosed by SCS macrophages and transferred into B cell follicles.⁴⁵

From the findings shown in **Figure 4B** that SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs and SG_{EDA-6} NPs localize within the paracortex area soon after the injection and that LG_{EDA-20} NPs remain confined within the peripheral SCS area, we can rule out the hypothesis that SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs and SG_{EDA-6} NPs are conveyed to the parenchyma by immune cells for the first 8–10 h of treatment.

It was recently found that 500 kDa antibody and dextran macromolecules were transferred to the parenchyma of draining LNs *via* a receptor independent, fluid-phase process of transcytosis of SCS lymphatic endothelial cells.⁴² We therefore hypothesized that SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs and SG_{EDA-6} NPs can enter the cortex through the same mechanism. In our previous studies, we have

shown that SG_{EDA-6} NPs cross the endothelial cell layer, human umbilical vein endothelial cells *via* exocytosis/transcytosis within 2 h of incubation.⁴⁶

Small Positively Charged Nanosugars Enable the Delivery of Small Cargo Molecules and

Antibodies to LNs *Via* SC Administration. To assess the versatility of the SG_{EDA-6} NPs, the delivery of small molecules to LN tissues was investigated using a fluorescent probe (AF488, 643 Da) as the model payload (SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs). SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs were prepared by exploiting electrostatic interactions between SG_{EDA-6} NPs and the small aromatic molecule.

Following SC injection of Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs at the left flank of the animals, IVIS analysis of the tissues 24 h post injection was conducted. Fluorescence signals from AF488 and Cy5.5 were detected at the site of injection and at axillary and inguinal LNs (**Figure 5A** and **Figures S14 and S15**). Moreover, confocal imaging of the tissue cryosections revealed stronger AF488 and Cy5.5 signals for the draining LN tissue (left) than for the contralateral tissue (right) and the phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) control (**Figure 5B**). SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs were detected at the SCS and the paracortex (**Figure 5C**), the latter displaying colocalization between the Cy5.5 and AF488 signals (**Figure 5D**). This analysis confirms the trafficking of functionally intact NCs to deeper areas of the tissue with available cargo for local intranodal delivery. We also studied the potential retention of the NCs at the ECM within the paracortex. For that purpose, we stained T cells with CD3 and the ECM within the LN tissue, specifically for fibronectin (**Figure S16A**) and collagen 1 (**Figure S16B**). Our results suggest that SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs are found in proximity to ECM components, which can partially explain their retention at the paracortex tissue area, 24 h post administration.

The delivery of antibodies (150 kDa) was also investigated. A fluorescence-labeled (RY586) anti-CD3 antibody was first complexed with SG_{EDA-6} NPs to form SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs and the

latter NCs were administered subcutaneously. As observed from **Figure 5E**, the NCs accumulated at the axillary and inguinal LNs. Thus, CD3 antibody was effectively delivered to both LNs—draining and nondraining contralateral LNs—after 24 h of incubation. Furthermore, the accumulation of antibodies at the draining LNs was significantly higher than that at the nondraining contralateral tissues (**Figure 5F**). Cryosections of the axillary LN tissues were further analyzed by confocal microscopy, which revealed delivery of anti-CD3 antibody within the LNs as observed by the intranodal labeling of T cells (pink, **Figure 5G**). These findings contrast those related to the direct SC delivery of antibodies, as reported in literature, which showed that after prolonged *in vivo* distribution, up to 24 h, antibody binding was restricted to the first draining LNs.⁴² This suggests that upon entry of the NCs in the blood flow, they remain functionally intact for delivery of the payload at the contralateral LNs. To confirm this hypothesis, a control experiment was performed by injecting anti-CD3 antibody in solution subcutaneously, at the left flank of the animals. Contrary to the findings reported in literature, under our experimental conditions, antibody accumulation was observed at both the draining and contralateral LNs when administered in its soluble form (**Figure 5H and 5I**). Specifically, when administered in its free form, the accumulation of antibody within the LNs was detected at one order of magnitude higher than that of the antibody delivered by SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs (10^8 *versus* 10^7), suggesting a slower and steady delivery achieved by the nanosugars. Similarly to SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs, SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs were observed in proximity of ECM components (**Figure S17A**), which most likely contributes to their longer retention and accumulation at the paracortex. Furthermore, one of the animals injected with free CD3 antibody displayed distinct increase in node size for both inguinal and axillary LNs, most likely owing to the onset of an inflammatory response (**Figure 5H, 5J and Figure S17B**). This may cause LN shutdown, which

restricts the egress of cells from the LNs and therefore the swelling of the tissue.⁴⁷ This effect was not observed when the antibody was delivered *via* NP loading, suggesting that the nanosugars represent a safer administration route for antibody accumulation at LNs.

The antibody accumulation at the LNs was also studied 15 min after SC administration. Our results revealed CD3 signal accumulation for the antibody administered in its free form or carried by nanosugars (SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs) as shown in **Figure S18A**. Comparison of the efficiency of antibody delivery in its free form and in SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs revealed significant accumulation differences for draining and contralateral LNs for the NCs, whereas the free CD3 antibody, which moved faster, displayed a lower degree of accumulation at the draining LNs and thus resulting in comparable accumulation in both draining and contralateral (**Figure S18B**). Confocal imaging of LNs treated with SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs shows the accumulation of NPs in the SCS region and the staining of CD3⁺ T cells in close proximity (**Figure S18C**), although no staining was detected within the paracortex T cell zone, recognized by T cell staining post tissue fixation (blue signal). This contrasts our observations at 24 h, suggesting that to access deeper paracortex areas, the saturation of the phagocytic capacity of the macrophages at the SCS is required.

Compared with IV injection, SC injection of monoclonal antibodies is thought to present higher immunogenicity *via* DC processing, as DCs are presented to the LNs in higher numbers from the subcutaneous layers. Herein, we show that using nanosugars as a carrier, we can circumvent this excessive immunogenic effect, while successfully delivering the antibody to the LN tissue with no dependency on DC transport.

Figure 5. Intact, nondegraded SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs and SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs accumulate at draining LNs. **(A)** Cy5.5 and AF488 fluorescence images and corresponding fluorescence quantification of axillary LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. Data are represented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 2$). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. $*p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.001$. **(B, C)** Representative confocal images of axillary LN tissues stained for CD169, CD3, and CD45R to identify macrophages, T cells, and B cells, respectively. Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6} NPs are identified in yellow. Scale bars in all images: 500 μm **(B)** and 100 μm **(C)**. **(D)** Corresponding Cy5.5 and AF488 signal distribution plots, for the regions marked (white squares) in the confocal images, show high signal colocalization in the SCS (i) and paracortex (ii) areas. **(E)** Ry586-CD3 fluorescence images of draining and non-draining contralateral inguinal and axillary LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. **(F)** Quantification of LN CD3 labeling based on IVIS imaging. Inguinal and axillary LNs from two treated animals were pooled for analysis. Statistical analysis was performed by paired t -test. $*p < 0.05$. Blue line corresponds to the signal for PBS-treated mice. **(G)** Representative confocal images of the axillary LN tissues stained for CD169 and CD45R to identify macrophages and B cells, respectively. The delivered CD3 antibody is detected in pink and the Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6} NPs are identified in yellow. Scale bars: 500 μm (main images) and 50 μm (for (iii)). **(H)** Ry586-CD3 fluorescence images of draining and non-draining contralateral inguinal and axillary LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. **(I)** Quantification of LN CD3 labeling based on IVIS imaging. Inguinal and axillary LNs from two treated animals were pooled for analysis. Blue line corresponds to the signal for PBS-treated mice. Statistical analysis was performed by paired t -test. $*p < 0.05$. **(J)**

Representative confocal images of the axillary LN tissues stained for CD169 and CD45R to identify macrophages and B cells, respectively. The delivered CD3 antibody is detected in pink and the Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6} NPs are identified in yellow. Scale bars: 500 μ m.

CONCLUSION

The biodistribution and accumulation of nanosugars, varying in size and surface charge, after SC administration, were investigated. Comprehensive imaging analyses revealed that small positively charged (SG_{EDANPs}) glycogen NPs allowed for better retention at LN tissues than negatively charged glycogen NPs (SG_{COOH} NPs), which transited through the lymph at a faster rate resulting in negligible intranodal accumulation. Super-resolution microscopy analyses showed that SG_{EDA} NPs mainly associated with macrophages (CD169⁺) at the SCS and medullary sinus. However, SG_{EDA} NPs also accumulated within deeper zones of the LN tissue, *i.e.*, the paracortex, rich in T cells (CD3⁺). Our findings suggested that SCS We also demonstrated that nanosugars could effectively carry and deliver different types of cargos to the LNs, including mRNA, small molecules, and antibodies, indicating the versatility of nanosugars for application in the potential treatment of lymphatic diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials. Phytoglycogen was purchased from Mirexus Biotechnology Inc. (Guelph, Canada) and bovine liver glycogen was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dialysis tubing (14 kDa) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS), EDA, deuterated water (D₂O), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), dibutylphthalate polystyrene xylene, sodium carbonate, 4% paraformaldehyde solution (PFA), wheat germ agglutinin, and conjugated primary antibodies fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) anti-mouse CD11c (11011482) and AF450

anti-mouse LYVE-1 (48044380) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Conjugate primary antibodies RY anti-mouse CD3 (568158) and AF488 anti-mouse CD45R (557669) were purchased from BD Biosciences. Conjugated anti-mouse antibodies BV 421 CD169 (142421), PE CD11c (117307), and FITC CD3 (100204) were purchased from BioLegend. Cre-recombinase (CRE1000M) and mFlame (MFLA1000M) mRNA were purchased from Messenger Bio (Australia). H&E staining kit was purchased from MedChem Express. 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine was purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Synthesis of SG_{EDA-6} NPs, SG_{EDA-27} NPs, and LG_{EDA-20} NPs. To prepare SG_{EDA-x} NPs and LG_{EDA-x} NPs (where *x* is the DS), glycogen from bovine liver (*i.e.*, SG NPs) and phytoglycogen (*i.e.*, LG NPs) (100 mg, corresponding to 0.6 mmol of glucose monomers), respectively, were first separately dissolved in acetate buffer (5 mL, 0.8 M, pH 5.5). To achieve DS of 6 and 20–27%, sodium periodate (6.6 and 26 mg, respectively) was added, and the solutions were stirred for 2 h in the dark. Then, EDA (10.3 and 40 μ L, respectively) and sodium cyanoborohydride (19.4 and 77 mg, respectively) were added. The pH was monitored and adjusted to 5.5 using 5 M HCl. The solution was stirred for 24 h in the dark. The final product was purified by dialysis (tube size 14 kDa) against sodium chloride (150 mM) for 1 day and against Milli-Q water for 5 days.

Synthesis of SG_{COOH} NPs and LG_{COOH} NPs. SG NPs or LG NPs (159 mg) were dissolved in anhydrous DMSO (9 mL) and placed under argon atmosphere at 40 °C. Next, succinic anhydride (27.8 mg) and 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine (34 mg) were dissolved in anhydrous DMSO (1.5 mL) and added to the SG NP or LG NP solution under argon atmosphere for 1 h. The mixture was left under stirring at 40 °C in oil bath for 4 days. After 4 days, HCl (0.31 mL 1.2 M) was added to neutralize 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine. The reaction product was purified by extensive dialysis

(tube size 10 kDa) against Milli-Q water for 5 days and freeze dried to afford SG_{COOH} NPs or LG_{COOH} NPs.

Cy5.5 labeling of Glycogen NPs. A known amount (2 mg) of glycogen NPs (nonmodified or modified) was dissolved in 100 mM bicarbonate buffer (0.5 mL, pH 9.2). Next, an aliquot (20 μ L for SG NPs or 40 μ L for LG NPs) of 1 mg mL⁻¹ Cy5.5 dye dissolved in DMSO was added. The solution was stirred for 25 h. A further purification step was performed to remove excess dye adsorbed onto the NP surface by dialysis in sodium chloride (150 mM) using a 14 kDa tube for 1 day and against Milli-Q water for 2 days to remove the salt.

Potentiometric Titration. To determine the degree of substitution, DS, 10 mL of LG_{COOH} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs suspensions at the concentration of 3 mg/mL were used. The pH of the suspension was adjusted to 3-4 using HCl (0.01 N). The suspension was then titrated using NaOH solution (0.01 N) by recording the pH as a function of the volume of HCl.

Complexation of SG_{EDA-6} NPs with AF488 or CD3. To prepare SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs or SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs, the binding efficiency between SG_{EDA-6} NPs and AF488 or antiCD3 antibody was first evaluated. AF488 was diluted 1:1 with Milli-Q water to a concentration of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹. The solution of AF488 (0.5 mg mL⁻¹) was then incubated at room temperature (23 °C) for 1 h to hydrolyze *N*-hydroxysuccinimide into carboxylic acid and prevent covalent linkage between the dye and SG_{EDA-6} NPs. Then, AF488 (15 μ L, 0.5 mg mL⁻¹) was mixed with SG_{EDA-6} NPs (1 mg), and Milli-Q water was added to achieve a final volume of 200 μ L and incubated at room temperature for 1 h. The entire mixture was loaded into prewetted spin columns with a 30 kDa molecular weight cutoff (Nanosep, OD003C33) and centrifuged at 9,000 g to concentrate the solution by approximately 2-fold. The centrifugation time was adjusted to target a final upper

volume of 100 μL . This step aimed to remove unbound dye and retain NCs in the unfiltered upper fraction. To quantify the dye content in the upper and lower fractions and assess binding efficiency, the absorbance of AF488 was measured at 488 nm on a NanoDrop2000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). A calibration curve was prepared for AF488, and linear regression analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism v.8.0 to correlate absorbance with concentration. The data revealed that all the dye was bound to the NPs, to obtain a final AF488 concentration of 0.075 mg mL^{-1} . Control experiments were conducted by processing an aliquot (200 μL) of each dye in Milli-Q water without NPs under identical conditions. To prepare SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs, an aliquot (5 μL) of SG_{EDA-6} NPs (30 mg mL^{-1}) and an aliquot (5 μL) of Ry586 Hamster anti-mouse CD3a (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) were added to $0.1\times$ PBS (110 μL) and incubated at room temperature for 1 h. Next, the mixture was filtered by spin column (100 kDa molecular weight cutoff) to remove the unbound antibody and quantify the efficiency of complexation. The efficiency of complexation (93%) was evaluated by comparing the fluorescence (excitation wavelength 565 nm; emission wavelength 586 nm) of the initial and filtered solutions

ζ -Potential and Hydrodynamic Diameter Measurements. ζ -Potential (in water) and hydrodynamic diameter distribution measurements were performed *via* DLS (Malvern Zetasizer NanoZS).

^1H NMR Spectroscopy. ^1H NMR spectra of aqueous solutions of glycogen NPs (modified) (1 mg mL^{-1}) were recorded on a 600 MHz Bruker Avance III at 40°C in H_2O and 10% D_2O . The data was processed using MestReNova software.

Degradation of Glycogen NPs by α -Amylase and β -Amylase. The rate of degradation of the glycogen NPs (nonmodified and modified) by α -amylase or β -amylase was determined using the Somogyi–Nelson assay. The NPs (200 μ L, 1 mg mL⁻¹) were first dissolved in PBS (10 mM, pH 7.4) and incubated at 37 °C with α -amylase (0.1 U mL⁻¹) or β -amylase (1 U mL⁻¹) for 3 h. For the assay, copper–carbonate–tartrate reagent was prepared. This first consisted of the preparation of stock I (sodium potassium tartrate tetrahydrate (1.2 g), sodium carbonate (2.4 g), sodium bicarbonate (1.6 g), and sodium sulfate (14.4 g) in Milli-Q water (80 mL)) and stock II (copper sulfate pentahydrate (0.4 g) and sodium sulfate (3.6 g) dissolved in Milli-Q water (20 mL)). The working reagent was then prepared by mixing 4 parts of stock I with 1 part of stock II. The arsenomolybdate color reagent was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate (2.5 g) in water, followed by mixing with concentrated sulfuric acid (2.1 mL). The resulting solution was mixed with a solution of sodium arsenate dibasic pentahydrate (0.3 g) in Milli-Q water (2.5 mL). Aliquots (45 μ L) of the glycogen NP solutions before and after treatment with amylases were mixed with the working reagent (45 μ L) in a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and heated at 90 °C for 20 min under dark (covered with aluminum foil) using a thermomixer. Triplicates were transferred to a 96-well microplate (Costar 3596, Corning, MA, USA) after cooling to room temperature, then the color reagent (45 μ L) was added to each well and mixed *via* pipetting and allowed to stand for 15 min before measurements. The absorbance was recorded at 600 nm using an Infinite M200 microplate reader (Tecan, Switzerland). For reference, glucose (considered as degraded glycogen) solutions at varying concentrations were prepared, and the absorbance was determined under the same conditions.

Animal studies. All animal experiments were performed according to the Australian code for the care and use of animals for scientific purposes and approved by the University of Melbourne

Animal Ethics Committee (Ethics nos. 10404 and 27608) and Monash University Animal Ethics Committee (Ethics AEC number E/P8230/2023). C57BL/6 mice (female, 6–8 weeks old) and B6.Cg-Gt(ROSA)26Sor^{tm14(CAG-tdTomato)Hze/J} mice⁴³ (common name: Ai14; mixed gender, 8–10 weeks old) were obtained from the BioResources Facility at the Peter Doherty Institute (Melbourne, Australia) and housed on a 12 h light/dark cycle with *ad libitum* access to food and water. C57BL/6 mice (male, 6–8 weeks old) were purchased from the Alfred Research Alliance Precinct Animal Centre (Australia) and mice were housed on a 12 h light/dark cycle with *ad libitum* access to food and water.

***In Vivo* Biodistribution Studies.** For the biodistribution studies of SG_{EDA-6} NPs, SG_{EDA-27} NPs, SG_{COOH} NPs, LG_{EDA-20} NPs, and SG_{COOH} NPs (**Figure 1**), C57BL mice (male, 8–10 weeks old) were used. The animals ($n \geq 2$) were injected in the left flank with the nanosugars (1200 μg NPs in 200 μL) and NP biodistribution monitoring was performed for up to a maximum of 24 h. The mice were euthanized by an overdose intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (300 mg kg^{-1}) and xylazine (30 mg kg^{-1}) and subsequently subjected to transcardial perfusion with PBS (10 mL) before harvest of axillary, cervical, brachial, and inguinal LNs and major organs, *i.e.*, liver, kidney, lung, heart, spleen, and brain. Subsequent imaging of the LNs and organs was conducted on an Odyssey CLx Scanner, with the fluorescence detected using the 700 nm (Cy5.5 dye) channel. Animal tissues collected in cold DPBS were fixed overnight in neutral buffered formalin.

For all remaining experiments, C57BL/6J mice (mixed gender, 6–10 weeks old) were used to study the biodistribution of SG_{EDA} NPs, SG_{EDA}-AF488 NCs, and SG_{EDA}-antiCD3 NCs. The animals ($n \geq 2$) were injected in the left flank with the nanosugars (200 μg NPs in 100 μL) and biodistribution monitoring was performed for up to a maximum of 24 h. The mice were

euthanized by CO₂ asphyxiation at designated time points. Axillary, cervical, brachial, and inguinal LNs and major organs, *i.e.*, liver, kidney, lung, heart, spleen, and brain, were harvested postinjection and imaged on IVIS (PerkinElmer, USA). Animal tissues collected in cold DPBS were fixed overnight in 4% PFA and then cryoprotected in 30% sucrose at 4 °C for at least 8 h. Then, the tissues were embedded in OCT compound and frozen over dry ice. The frozen specimens were conserved at –80 °C and then sectioned into 7 μm sections using a cryostat (Leica Biosystems, Australia).

***In Vivo* mRNA Delivery.** C57BL/6J mice (mixed gender, 8–10 weeks old) or Ai14 mice (mixed gender, 8–10 weeks old) were divided into 2 groups ($n = 3$ per group): DPBS control and groups treated with S_{GEDA} NPs (200 μg per animal) or S_{GEDA}-mRNA NCs (200 μg NPs containing 10 μg mRNA per animal). Each group underwent SC injection at the left flank for a total volume of 100 μL. Cre mRNA (10 μg per animal) or mFlame mRNA (10 μg per animal) were used to transfect Ai14 or C57BL/6J mice, respectively. The mice were euthanized by CO₂ asphyxiation at designated time points. Axillary, cervical, brachial, and inguinal LNs and major organs, *i.e.*, liver, kidney, lung, heart, spleen, and brain, were harvested postinjection and imaged on IVIS. Animal tissues collected in cold DPBS were fixed overnight in 4% PFA and then cryoprotected in 30% sucrose at 4 °C for at least 8 h. Then, the tissues were embedded in OCT compound and frozen over dry ice. The frozen specimens were conserved at –80°C and later sectioned into 7 μm sections using a cryostat.

Tissue Histology. After cryosectioning, tissue histology was assessed by H&E staining. Briefly, the tissues were thoroughly washed with 1× DPBS for 5 times for 3 min and then stained with hematoxylin for 3 min. Post incubation, the tissue samples were washed with tap water to remove excess stain. Following the washing step, the slides were sequentially dehydrated using

50–70–96% ethanol and incubated in eosin for 2 min. Then, the slides were washed three times in absolute ethanol, and the tissues were cleared by incubating in xylene for 1 min. The stained tissues were mounted onto a coverslip using dibutyl phthalate polystyrene xylene and dried overnight.

Tissue Immunohistochemistry. The tissue sections were thawed at room temperature (5–10 min) and rehydrated in DPBS for 5 min. Next, samples were permeabilized with 0.2% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature. After a washing step, blocking was performed using 2.5% bovine serum albumin in DPBS for 30 min at room temperature. Primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4 °C at the following dilutions: RY CD3 (1:400), FITC CD3 (1:100), AF488 CD45R (1:200), BV 421 CD169 (1:50), PE CD11c (1:50), FITC CD11c (1:50), and AF450 LYVE-1 (1:50). Tissues were imaged using a Nikon A1R+ confocal microscope or a Zeiss Elyra 7 Lattice SIM system.

Characterization of Glycogen NPs by STORM Imaging. For STORM analysis of Cy5.5-labeled glycogen NPs (modified), the NPs were deposited on a glass slide at 25 °C for 30 min. Then, unbound molecules and NCs were washed away with freshly prepared, standard imaging buffer with cysteamine. For cryosection tissue analysis, the tissues were allowed to thaw at room temperature for 5 min and then the OCT compound washed out with PBS followed by immersion in standard imaging buffer with cysteamine. STORM images were acquired using a Nikon N-STORM system equipped with a Nikon 100 × 1.4 NA oil immersion objective. The focus and the total internal reflection fluorescence imaging angle were adjusted to obtain a high signal-to-noise ratio. A 647 nm laser was used for excitation of the Cy5.5 fluorophores. All time lapses were recorded within a 256 pixels × 256 pixels region using an EMCCD camera. For each image, 4000 frames were acquired sequentially using full laser power. STORM images were first

processed with the STORM module of the NIS Elements Nikon software, where drift correction was performed, and a list of particle localizations were obtained by Gaussian fitting of the fluorescence spots of blinking dyes. Blinking events that were detected in ≤ 5 consecutive frames were counted as single molecules, whereas events detected in more than 5 consecutive frames were discarded (maximum trace length 5). The list of localizations was exported as a text file and analyzed using a Python clustering analysis script where the localizations were clustered using a kernel density estimation with a bandwidth of 50 nm. An ellipse was fitted to the obtained clusters with a minimum of 10 localizations and a maximum elongation factor of 1.5 (ratio of long and short axes of the ellipse). Then, the circles containing 90% of detected spots in the cluster were fitted, allowing for the determination of the particle size distribution and number of localizations.

Image Analysis. All images acquired by SIM and confocal microscopy were analyzed using Image J.

Statistical Analysis. All results are shown as mean \pm standard deviation. The statistical significance and *p* values were determined with GraphPad Prism 8 or 10 using the tests specified in the figure captions.

Minimum Information Reporting in Bio–Nano Experimental Literature (MIRIBEL). The studies conducted herein, including material characterization, biological characterization, and experimental details, conform to the MIRIBEL reporting standard for bio–nano research,⁴⁸ and we include a companion checklist of these components in the Supporting Information.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Characterization of glycogen NPs; ¹H NMR spectra of modified glycogen NPs; percentage of nanosugars detected in blood; *in vivo* histology characterization; STORM characterization of glycogen NPs and NCs; representative confocal images of animal tissues after glycogen NP/NC administration; biodistribution profiles of glycogen NPs and NCs; and MIRIBEL checklist.

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

F.Caruso is a shareholder of Messenger Bio Pty. Ltd. All other authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Supporting Information

Trafficking Nanosugars through Lymph Node Tissues for the Delivery of Small and Large Bioactive Molecules

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Table S1. Glycogen NP characterization

NP System	Size [nm] ^{a)}	ζ-Potential [mV]	DS [%]	α-Amylase [%]	β-Amylase [%]
LG NPs	45 ± 12	-1 ± 2	Not applicable	6.8 ± 0.7	40 ± 8
SG NPs	14 ± 4	-6 ± 2	Not applicable	24 ± 1	42 ± 5
LG _{EDA-20} NPs	57 ± 2	54 ± 9	20	7.6 ± 0.4	12 ± 1
SG _{EDA-27} NPs	19 ± 2	53 ± 4	27	15 ± 2	3 ± 1
SG _{EDA-6} NPs	16 ± 4	10 ± 6	6	15 ± 0.4	9 ± 1
LG _{COOH} NPs	43 ± 12	-36 ± 3	17	7 ± 1	8 ± 1
SG _{COOH} NPs	13 ± 4	-27 ± 1	14	10 ± 2	Not measured
SG _{EDA-6} -mRNA NCs	55 ± 34 ^{b)}	2 ± 5	6	Not measured	Not measured
SG _{EDA-27} -mRNA NCs	220 ± 100	33 ± 4	27	Not measured	Not measured
SG _{EDA-6} -AF488 NCs	28 ± 20 ^{b)}	10 ± 2	6	Not measured	Not measured
SG _{EDA-6} -antiCD3 NCs	24 ± 8 ^{b)}	13 ± 3	6	Not measured	Not measured

^{a)} Number size distribution (unless stated otherwise) determined by dynamic light scattering

^{b)} Intensity size distribution determined by dynamic light scattering

DS – degree of substitution; LG – large glycogen; NPs – nanoparticles; SG – small glycogen; EDA – ethylenediamine; COOH – carboxylic acid.

Figure S1. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of (A) $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-6}}$ NPs with DS 6%, (B) $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-27}}$ NPs with DS 27%, (C) SG_{COOH} NPs, (D) $\text{LG}_{\text{EDA-20}}$ with DS 20%, and (E) LG_{COOH} NPs.

Figure S2. Potentiometric titration curves of (A) LG_{COOH} NPs and (B) SG_{COOH} NPs, displaying changes in pH as a function of NaOH addition.

Figure S3. Percentage of nanosugars detected in blood during the first 24 h post SC injection.

Figure S4. Representative H&E staining of tissues of mice treated with various nanosugars 1 h after SC administration.

Figure S5. Representative confocal image of inguinal LN harvested 5 h after administration of SG_{EDA-27} NPs. AF647-labeled NPs, macrophages, B cells, and T cells are identified in cyan, yellow, green, and red, respectively. Scale bar: 500 μ m.

Figure S6. Representative STORM images of Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-27} NPs and SG_{COOH} NPs.

Figure S7. Representative confocal images of popliteal LN harvested 1 h or 5 h after administration of positively charged NPs ($\text{LG}_{\text{EDA-20}}$ NPs). AF647-labeled NPs are identified in cyan. Scale bars: 500 μm .

Figure S8. Size distribution and representative STORM microscopy images of Cy5.5-labeled $\text{SG}_{\text{EDA-6}}$ -mRNA NCs.

Figure S9. SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs accumulate at injection site, 24 h after SC administration. Representative confocal images of cryosectioned skin tissues at the injection site. Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs are identified in yellow. Cell membranes were stained with wheat germ agglutinin (WGA, red) and nuclei with Hoechst (white). Scale bars for all images: 100 μ m.

Figure S10. *In vivo* biodistribution and transfection potential of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs administered intravenously. Cy5.5 fluorescence images, acquired by IVIS, of (A) major organs and (B) LNs harvested 24 h after intravenous injection of SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs loaded with mRNA encoding for mFlame (ζ -potential 10 mV) in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. mFlame expression fluorescence images of (C) major organs and (D) LNs. Data are represented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 2$). Statistical analyses were performed two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure S11. *In vivo* transfection potential of naked Cre mRNA. tdTomato expression fluorescence images of skin, major organs, and LNs 24 h after Cre mRNA administration to the left flank of C57BL/6J mice.

Figure S12. *In vivo* biodistribution and transfection potential of SG_{EDA-27}-mRNA NCs (ζ -potential 53 mV) administered subcutaneously. Cy5.5 fluorescence images, acquired by IVIS, of (A) skin, (B) major organs, and (C) LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-27} NPs (ζ -potential 19 mV) loaded with Cre mRNA, in the left flank of Ai14 mice. (D) tdTomato expression fluorescence image of the skin. (E) Representative confocal images of LN tissue stained for CD169, CD3, and CD45R to identify macrophages, T cells, and B cells, respectively. Scale bar for all images: 500 μ m. Data are represented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 2$). Statistical analyses were performed by unpaired *t*-test or two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure S13. Representative confocal images of axillary LN stained for CD169, CD3, and CD45R to identify macrophages, T cells, and B cells, respectively. Tissues from (A) control mice injected with PBS (*i.e.*, no NCs) and (B) mice injected with SG_{EDA-6}-mRNA NCs. Scale bars: 500 μ m (magnified images).

Figure S14. Representative confocal images of axillary LN tissues treated with SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs. Tissues were stained for CD169 and CD3 to identify macrophages and T cells, respectively. Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs are shown in yellow. AF488 fluorescence signal is shown in green. Scale bars for all images: 500 μ m.

Figure S15. (A) Cy5.5 and AF488 fluorescence images, and fluorescence quantification, of inguinal LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. Data are represented as mean ± standard deviation ($n = 2$). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. $*p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.001$. (B) Representative confocal images of axillary LN tissues treated with PBS or SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs. Scale bars: 500 μm. (C) Tissues were stained for CD169 and CD3 to

identify macrophages and T cells, respectively. Cy5.5-labeled SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs are shown in yellow. AF488 fluorescence signal is shown in green. Scale bars for all images: 100 μ m. Corresponding Cy5.5 and AF488 signal distribution plots, for the regions marked by the red arrows in the confocal images, showing high signal colocalization in the SCS and paracortex areas.

Figure S16. (A, B) Representative confocal images of LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-AF488 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. The tissues were stained for T cells with antiCD3 antibody (pink) and fibronectin (A) or anti-collagen 1 (B) in blue. Cy5.5 and AF488 fluorescence signals are identified in yellow and green, respectively. Scale bars: 100 μ m and 50 μ m (magnified areas). Red triangles identify NCs in proximity of ECM components.

Figure S17. (A) Representative confocal images of LNs harvested 24 h after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. The tissues were stained for fibronectin (blue) and CD169⁺ macrophages (white). Cy5.5 and RY586-CD3 fluorescence signals are identified in yellow and pink, respectively. Scale bars: 100 μ m and 50 μ m (magnified area). Red triangles identify NCs in proximity to fibronectin. (B) Representative confocal images of inguinal LN tissues, 24 h after SC injection of antiCD3 antibody. The tissue is stained for CD169 and CD45R to identify macrophages and B cells, respectively. The delivered CD3 antibody is detected in pink. . Scale bars: 1000 μ m.

Figure S18. SC injection of antiCD3 antibody and SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs for 15 min. (A) Cy5.5 and RY586-CD3 fluorescence images of inguinal and axillary LNs harvested 15 min after SC injection of SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs in the left flank of C57BL/6 mice. (B) Quantification of LN CD3 labeling based on IVIS imaging. Inguinal and axillary LNs from two treated animals were pooled for analysis. Statistical analysis was performed by paired *t*-test. (C) Representative confocal images of axillary LN tissues treated with SG_{EDA-6}-antiCD3 NCs. Tissues were stained with another antiCD3 antibody (blue) post tissue fixation. Scale bars: 500 μm (entire LN tissue) and 100 μm (magnified areas).

Supplementary Table 1. Material characterization*

Question	Yes	No
1.1 Are “ best reporting practices ” available for the nanomaterial used? For examples, see <i>Chem. Mater.</i> 28 (2016) 3535; http://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b01854 and <i>Chem. Mater.</i> 29 (2017) 1; http://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b05235	Not applicable	
1.2 If they are available, are they used ? If not available, ignore this question and proceed to the next one.		
1.3 Are extensive and clear instructions reported detailing all steps of synthesis and the resulting composition of the nanomaterial? For examples, see <i>Chem. Mater.</i> 26 (2014) 1765; http://doi.org/10.1021/cm500632c , and <i>Chem. Mater.</i> 26 (2014) 2211; http://doi.org/10.1021/cm5010449 . Extensive use of photos, images, and videos are strongly encouraged. For example, see <i>Chem. Mater.</i> 28 (2016) 8441; http://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b04639	√	
1.4 Is the size (or dimensions , if non-spherical) and shape of the nanomaterial reported?	√	
1.5 Is the size dispersity or aggregation of the nanomaterial reported?	√	
1.6 Is the zeta potential of the nanomaterial reported?	√	
1.7 Is the density (mass/volume) of the nanomaterial reported?	√	
1.8 Is the amount of any drug loaded reported? ‘Drug’ here broadly refers to functional cargos (e.g., proteins, small molecules, nucleic acids).	√	
1.9 Is the targeting performance of the nanomaterial reported, including amount of ligand bound to the nanomaterial if the material has been functionalised through addition of targeting ligands?	Not applicable	
1.10 Is the label signal per nanomaterial/particle reported? For example, fluorescence signal per particle for fluorescently labelled nanomaterials.	√	
1.11 If a material property not listed here is varied, has it been quantified ?	Not applicable	
1.12 Were characterizations performed in a fluid mimicking biological conditions ?	√	
1.13 Are details of how these parameters were measured/estimated provided?	√	
Explanation for No (if needed):		

*Ideally, material characterization should be performed in the same biological environment as that in which the study will be conducted. For example, for cell culture studies with nanoparticles, characterization steps would ideally be performed on nanoparticles dispersed in cell culture media. If this is not possible, then characteristics of the dispersant used (e.g., pH, ionic strength) should mimic as much as possible the biological environment being studied.

Supplementary Table 2. Biological characterization*

Question	Yes	No
2.1 Are cell seeding details , including number of cells plated, confluency at start of experiment , and time between seeding and experiment reported?	Not applicable	
2.2 If a standardised cell line is used, are the designation and source provided?	Not applicable	
2.3 Is the passage number (total number of times a cell culture has been subcultured) known and reported?	Not applicable	
2.4 Is the last instance of verification of cell line reported? If no verification has been performed, is the time passed and passage number since acquisition from trusted source (e.g., ATCC or ECACC) reported? For information, see <i>Science</i> 347 (2015) 938; http://doi.org/10.1126/science.347.6225.938	Not applicable	
2.5 Are the results from mycoplasma testing of cell cultures reported?	Not applicable	
2.6 Is the background signal of cells/tissue reported? (E.g., the fluorescence signal of cells without particles in the case of a flow cytometry experiment.)	√	
2.7 Are toxicity studies provided to demonstrate that the material has the expected toxicity, and that the experimental protocol followed does not?	Not applicable	
2.8 Are details of media preparation (type of media, serum, any added antibiotics) provided?	Not applicable	
2.9 Is a justification of the biological model used provided? For examples for cancer models, see <i>Cancer Res.</i> 75 (2015) 4016; http://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-15-1558 , and <i>Mol. Ther.</i> 20 (2012) 882; http://doi.org/10.1038/mt.2012.73 , and <i>ACS Nano</i> 11 (2017) 9594; http://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.7b04855	√	
2.10 Is characterization of the biological fluid (<i>ex vivo/in vitro</i>) reported? For example, when investigating protein adsorption onto nanoparticles dispersed in blood serum, pertinent aspects of the blood serum should be characterised (e.g., protein concentrations and differences between donors used in study).	√	
2.11 For animal experiments , are the ARRIVE guidelines followed? For details, see <i>PLOS Biol.</i> 8 (2010) e1000412; http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1000412	√	
Explanation for No (if needed):		

*For *in vitro* experiments (e.g., cell culture), *ex vivo* experiments (e.g., in blood samples), and *in vivo* experiments (e.g., animal models). The questions above that are appropriate depend on the type of experiment conducted.

Supplementary Table 3. Experimental details*

Question	Yes	No
3.1 For cell culture experiments: are cell culture dimensions including type of well, volume of added media , reported? Are cell types (i.e.; adherent vs suspension) and orientation (if non-standard) reported?	Not applicable	
3.2 Is the dose of material administered reported? This is typically provided in nanomaterial mass, volume, number, or surface area added. Is sufficient information reported so that regardless of which one is provided, the other dosage metrics can be calculated (i.e. using the dimensions and density of the nanomaterial)?	√	
3.3 For each type of imaging performed, are details of how imaging was performed provided, including details of shielding, non-uniform image processing , and any contrast agents added?	√	
3.4 Are details of how the dose was administered provided, including method of administration, injection location, rate of administration , and details of multiple injections ?	√	
3.5 Is the methodology used to equalise dosage provided?		√
3.6 Is the delivered dose to tissues and/or organs (in vivo) reported, as % injected dose per gram of tissue (%ID g ⁻¹)?		√
3.7 Is mass of each organ/tissue measured and mass of material reported?		√
3.8 Are the signals of cells/tissues with nanomaterials reported? For instance, for fluorescently labelled nanoparticles, the total number of particles per cell or the fluorescence intensity of particles + cells, at each assessed timepoint.	√	
3.9 Are data analysis details , including code used for analysis provided?	√	
3.10 Is the raw data or distribution of values underlying the reported results provided? For examples, see <i>R. Soc. Open Sci.</i> 3 (2016) 150547; http://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.150547 , https://opennessinitiative.org/making-your-data-public/ , http://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability , and https://www.nature.com/sdata/policies/repositories		√
Explanation for No (if needed): 3.6. Reported only for blood (Figure S3). 3.7. Mass of tissue is not reported but the mass of nanoparticles used is reported.		

* The use of protocol repositories (e.g., *Protocol Exchange* <http://www.nature.com/protocolexchange/>) and published standard methods and protocols (e.g., *Chem. Mater.* **29** (2017) 1; <http://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b05235>, and *Chem. Mater.* **29** (2017) 475; <http://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b05481>) are encouraged.